

Green Startup Report 2025

BORDERSTEP INSTITUTE
for Innovation and Sustainability
Science with Impact

Alexander Bonde

Secretary General of the German
Federal Environmental Foundation

Foreword

“It’s the economy, stupid!” More than thirty years ago, Bill Clinton coined this slogan during the U.S. presidential campaign. Much has happened since then – economically and politically, scientifically and ecologically.

Today we know: **it’s the ecology, stupid!**

We must not forget that a healthy environment is the foundation for successful economic activity. Especially in economically and politically challenging times, it is crucial that we stay on course and continue to invest in sustainable innovations.

The World Economic Forum’s Global Risk Report 2025* underscores the importance of protecting the climate and biodiversity. According to the report, extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem collapse are among the greatest risks of the next ten years. These environmental threats are not just long-term challenges – they also pose immediate risks to our society and economy. The findings make it clear: action is needed to minimize these risks and secure a sustainable future.

* Elsner et al. (2025)

Green start-ups play a central role in this effort. They are the pioneers who, with their innovative ideas and technologies, are paving the way for a sustainable economy. These companies demonstrate that economic success and ecological responsibility can go hand in hand. They prove that it is possible to develop and implement sustainable business models even in difficult times.

The Green Startup Report 2025 provides a comprehensive, detailed, and encouraging overview of the current state and development of green start-ups in Germany. It lays the foundation for how sustainable economic growth can succeed..

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Alexander Bonde'.

Sincerely,

Alexander Bonde

Secretary General of the German
Federal Environmental Foundation (DBU)

Preface

Green Economy
Gründungsmonitor

2013

2014

2015

2016

2017

2018

Green Startup
Monitor

2019

2020

2021

2022

2023

2024

Green Startup
Report

2025

2026

Since 2013, the Borderstep Institute has published annual data on green start-ups and new ventures in Germany. We have continuously improved the coverage, analysis methodology, and informative value of our data. With the Green Startup Report 2025, we are taking monitoring to the next level.

The report is based on a comprehensive record of all start-ups in Germany that are registered as corporations (e.g., UG, GmbH, AG, etc.). The findings are drawn from around 18,000 commercial register entries for start-ups and over 50,000 records of investments in these companies. In addition, we no longer rely on the self-assessment of start-ups to determine whether they are „green“ or not. Instead, we evaluate the environmental performance of their products and services using a rigorous scientific methodology, drawing on the classification of environmental

goods and services as defined by the European statistical office EUROSTAT*.

We are also breaking new ground in other areas. With the GSR 2025, we present—for the first time worldwide—data on the climate mitigation potential of young, innovative companies, based on the Borderstep Institute’s Impact Database. In our new “Spotlights” section, we invite colleagues from the research community to share their latest findings and insights on green start-ups and their specific challenges and opportunities. In doing so, we are expanding the data and knowledge base on what drives success and how ecosystems must be shaped to support it.

In the past, the data, findings, and recommendations from our publications have been widely received by policymakers, fund-

ing institutions, and the start-up ecosystem—something we are proud of. With the strong and growing network of partners behind the Green Startup Report 2025, our findings are now reaching an even broader audience. In this way, we are living up to our mission of delivering “science with impact” and contributing, through scientific means, to the major transformation challenges of our time.

Prof. Dr. Klaus Fichter

Director
Borderstep Institute for
Innovation and Sustainability

* European Commission: Eurostat (2016)

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Goals of the Green Startup Report and definition of green Start-ups

Characteristics of green start-ups

- > Start-ups are **less than 10 years old**,
- > are **(highly) innovative** and/or have **(planned) employee or revenue growth**,
- > and contribute through their **products and services** to the environmental goals of a Green Economy.

The **NEW** Green Startup Report 2025

New **data basis**

Commercial register data

- › **17,954 commercial register entries** on innovative and growth-orientated start-ups (identified by startupdetector)
- › **53,034 commercial register entries** for investments made in start-ups

Environmental assessment by scientific team

- › by means of a multi-stage evaluation and validation process
- › based on the EUROSTAT * sector classification for environmental goods and services
- › Evaluation of the start-ups' websites and other documents

Borderstep database on climate mitigation potential

- › Database on the climate mitigation potential of green start-ups' products/services based on innovative impact forecasting methodology

Advantages of the new data basis

- › The comprehensive recording of all start-ups in the legal form of a corporation based on commercial register data allows a generalisation of the findings as well as the analysis of absolute figures with a high degree of timeliness.
- › The non-anonymised data allows a methodologically sound and reliable categorisation into green and non-green start-ups.
- › The objective data basis (as opposed to a self-assessment) allows for more robust results and a more nuanced view and analysis of green start-ups. Distortions due to socially desirable answers can be excluded.
- › The new database enables a look at new areas of the start-up ecosystem, such as the support and financing landscape, as well as a link to previously untapped data sources on start-up actors, investments and innovations.

Spotlights: more voices and insights from the ecosystem

- › For the first time, we are inviting other researchers and practice partners to prepare important findings and insights on green start-ups and the sustainability of the start-up ecosystem in a short form for the GSR.
- › Spotlights from the work of other important players from research and practice strengthen the GSR as an information base for the green start-up ecosystem.
- › Findings from different data bases and analyses enable new and different perspectives and inspire the research and implementation agenda.

🔗 [Detailed description of the methodology on pages 35-37](#)

* European Commission: Eurostat (2016)

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important facts from the GSR 2025

Green start-ups on the road to success

More and more young companies are focussing on sustainability! One in five start-ups is now developing innovative products and services that demonstrably protect the environment and climate. Green business ideas are particularly well represented among growth-orientated start-ups with investment (29%).

Enormous climate mitigation potential

For the first time, the GSR provides figures worldwide on the climate mitigation potential of young innovative companies. On average, the potential of a single transformation-oriented green start-up is 30,000 tonnes of CO₂e per year. This corresponds to a value of around € 2.4 million in the EU emissions trading system.

Women more often in the management

At 22 %, the proportion of women in the management of green start-ups is significantly higher than in non-green start-ups (17 %). This indicates that sustainable business models are more attractive to female founders and/or that green start-ups are more willing to actively embrace and promote diversity in management roles.

NRW: pioneer of green start-up support

The support landscape of a single federal state was analysed for the first time. 86 % of green start-ups in NRW rate the start-up ecosystem that has been developed over the last ten years as good or very good. Satisfaction with green start-up support is therefore well above the national average of 56 %.

EXIST & HTGF greener than average

Although green start-ups do not receive any specific environmental incentives from EXIST and High-Tech Gründerfonds, they are represented above average. Among EXIST grantees, the proportion was 33 % in 2024. This shows their technological and economic attractiveness.

Use of AI and critical reflection

88 % of the green start-ups surveyed already use generative AI, particularly for marketing and sales. At the same time, 34 % see the use of generative AI as a significant risk to their sustainable mission and integrity, partly due to the high energy consumption.

Funds increasingly focus on on climate mitigation

73 % of fund managers take climate aspects into account when making investment decisions - driven by regulatory requirements, optimisation of portfolio performance and ethical responsibility, among other things.

“The figures show: The motivation to found green start-ups based on science is increasing. Venture capital investors regard start-ups in this field as attractive investment objects. The EXIST and High-Tech Gründerfonds funding programmes also make an important contribution here with an above-average proportion of green start-ups. In this way, we are putting green start-ups on the road to success through targeted support - for real added value for the climate and society.” (Editors translation*)

Dr. Armgard Wippler
Head of the “SME and Start-up Financing, KfW” sub-department at BMWK

1

GREEN START-UPS: DISTRIBUTION, CHARACTERISTICS AND FINANCING

* Original quote: „Die Zahlen zeigen: Die Motivation, grüne Startups aus der Wissenschaft heraus zu gründen, steigt. Risikokapitalinvestoren betrachten Start-ups in diesem Bereich als attraktive Anlageobjekte. Auch die Förderprogramme EXIST und High-Tech Gründerfonds leisten hier einen wichtigen Beitrag mit einem überdurchschnittlichen Anteil grüner Start-ups. So bringen wir durch gezielte Unterstützung grüne Start-ups auf die Erfolgsspur – für echten Mehrwert für Klima und Gesellschaft.“
Dr. Armgard Wippler – Leiterin der Unterabteilung „Mittelstands- und Start-up-Finanzierung, KfW“ im BMWK

Heterogeneous distribution of green start-ups in Germany

By far the largest number of green start-ups identified (21%) came from the Berlin region, followed by Upper Bavaria (13%), Cologne (8%), Hamburg (6%) and Darmstadt (6%).

There is a north-south divide in the proportion of green start-ups among all start-ups in a federal state. Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania is the clear leader here with 27%, followed by Bremen (25%), Brandenburg (21%) and Schleswig-Holstein (20%).

➔ Distribution of green start-ups by administrative districts (NUTS-2, average value for the years 2019 - 2024)

➔ Share of green start-ups in the respective federal state (NUTS-1, average value for the years 2019 - 2024)

Based on the analysis of 2,113 green and 10,148 non-green start-ups founded between 2019 and 2024.

The share of green start-ups is steadily increasing

One in five start-ups founded in Germany in 2023 can be classified as green on the basis of the GSR's new data and more precise categorisation method*.

Start-ups in which investments have already been made have an above-average number of green products and services. Almost three out of ten start-ups with investment can be categorised as green.

➔ Share of green start-ups in all start-ups founded in the respective year (2019 – 2023 in %)

- share of all start-ups with investments
- share of all start-ups

Based on the analysis of 10,542 start-ups founded in the years 2019 to 2023, of which 2,883 start-ups received investments.

*For research design and methodology see [Page 36](#)

Women are more often in charge in green start-ups

The share of start-ups in which women are on the management board according to the commercial register is significantly higher among green start-ups.

This higher presence of women confirms previous study results (e.g. in the Green Startup Monitor 2024*) and underlines the assumption that sustainability-oriented start-ups are particularly attractive to women.

At the same time, it points to the greater willingness of green start-ups to actively embrace and promote diversity in leadership roles. It thus underlines the importance of green start-ups for a more diverse start-up landscape.

➔ Start-ups with women in management

Based on the analysis of 2,019 green and 9,506 non-green start-ups founded between 2019 and 2024.

➔ **Key start-up types** in the green start-up scene according to customer groups, field of activity and value creation logic

Based on the analysis of 1,724 green start-ups founded between 2019 and 2023: two-step cluster analysis, ratio of distance measures: 1.862; ratio of cluster size: 1.49; average silhouette: 0.4. Listed are the most defining attributes within each cluster.

Green start-ups can be categorized into **three types**

The strong presence of **hardware start-ups** (28%), which was already a key feature of the green start-up scene in previous editions of the Green Startup Monitor, underlines the importance of technological innovations for key sustainability areas such as energy and mobility.

The high proportion of start-ups with **green consumer products** (30%) illustrates the relevance of sustainable consumer goods in the green start-up landscape. E-commerce and food are particularly important here.

The high proportion of **SaaS and platform solutions** (42%) reflects the trend towards digitalization and data-based optimization, which helps companies to use resources more efficiently.

Although the three start-up types are clearly distinguishable, the fields of activity of hardware and SaaS/platform start-ups overlap; an indication of the high demand for combined technologies in key transformation fields such as energy, mobility and the environment.

Distribution of green start-up types shows clear regional focal points

➔ **Distribution of the green start-up types** in selected federal states (2019 - 2023 in %)

- green hardware start-ups
- green consumer product start-ups
- green software and platform start-ups

Based on the analysis of 1,717 green start-ups, 1,168 of which were in the federal states shown (BW: 191, BY: 324, BE: 368, MV: 20, NW: 265).

The capital city of **Berlin** has the highest share of green software and platform start-ups, which confirms its role as a digital innovation center. At the same time, the share of green hardware start-ups (19%) is well below the national average (28%).

Bavaria, North Rhine-Westphalia and Baden-Württemberg have similar shares in the three categories and largely reflect the nationwide structure. However, they appear to benefit from strong industrial networks (hardware) and an attractive market for green consumer products.

The above-average share of green hardware start-ups in **Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania** (50% vs. 28% national average) indicates a specialization in technology and research-intensive areas. At the same time, the share of green consumer product start-ups remains well below the average (30%) at 20%, which indicates a lower market dynamic in the end customer business.

Green start-ups are increasingly attractive for funding and financing

➔ Share of green start-ups in all start-ups founded between 2019 and 2024 ...

At 24%, the share of green start-ups among all start-ups founded with investment since 2019 is significantly higher than that of start-ups without investment (15%).

Technology and science-based start-ups are also green to an above-average extent: 25% of start-ups financed by the High-Tech Gründerfonds (HTGF) and 26% of start-ups funded by EXIST programs belong to the green economy.

The share of financed green start-ups is rising continuously. In the EXIST programs, for example, their share has increased by 10 percentage points to 33% since 2019.

➔ Share of green start-ups in all EXIST-funded start-ups

It is worth noting that green start-ups do not receive an environmental bonus in either the HTGF or the EXIST programs. This is confirmed by previous studies that point to their above-average economic attractiveness*.

Based on an analysis of the years 2019 to 2024 of a total of 2,965 start-ups that received an investment, 128 start-ups that received HTGF funding and 571 start-ups that received EXIST funding.

* Neumann (2023)

Public funding and investments set different priorities

The funding programs examined focus heavily on technology-driven green start-ups, while investors take a broader perspective.

- ➔ **EXIST & DBU** primarily support green software and platform start-ups (47% and 48% respectively) and green hardware start-ups (46% and 43% respectively), while green consumer product start-ups are barely considered (7% and 9% respectively). This indicates that consumer-oriented start-ups are less likely to be created in close proximity to universities and science (EXIST) or that their solutions are less frequently perceived as a significant lever with an environmental focus (DBU).
- ➔ The **HTGF** has a clear focus on green hardware start-ups (59%), while green software and platform start-ups are also still relevant at 41%.

Green consumer product start-ups do not receive any funding here, as HTGF primarily supports technology and research-based business models.

- ➔ **Investors**, on the other hand, distribute their capital more broadly: green software and platform (42%) and green hardware start-ups (32%) continue to dominate, but green consumer product start-ups (26%) receive significantly more support here than through the funding programs examined. This shows that, in addition to technological innovation, investors also focus strongly on market potential and direct scalability.

➔ **Distribution of green start-up types among all green start-ups in selected funding programs and investments**
2019 – 2023 (in %)

Based on the analysis of 1,724 green start-ups (125 EXIST-, 46 DBU-, 32 HTGF-funded, 682 with investment).

2 | CLIMATE MITIGATION POTENTIAL OF GREEN START-UPS

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Green start-ups demonstrably contribute to compliance with the Paris Climate Agreement and thus to a reduction in the economic damage caused by the climate emergency. They also show ways in which new technologies, such as AI, can be used to meet the Paris climate target. The faster green start-ups grow, the faster the positive benefits for society as a whole grow.

Ruth von Heusinger, Founder and Managing Director of ForTomorrow

”

Climate mitigation potential of green start-ups examined for the first time

Green start-ups generate a **double dividend**: In addition to economic added value (jobs, profits, etc.), they also create ecological added value with their innovative products and services - for example through climate and nature conservation or improved resource efficiency.

While there are established indicators and assessment methods for economic performance, it was previously unclear how big the ecological impact and potential of green start-ups is. With the **GHG & Impact Estimator** - a new, innovative methodology - the Borderstep Institute has now quantified the concrete **climate mitigation potential of green start-ups** for the first time and created an impact database.

The results presented here relate to the subgroup of **transformation-oriented green**

start-ups that strongly prioritize ecological and/or social sustainability goals as well as rapid growth and a high market share. *

The **climate mitigation potential depends**, among other things, **on the development phase, the age and the planned realistic sales growth** of the start-up. A direct comparison of the results of individual start-ups only makes sense if the assumptions are examined in detail.

The methodology in brief:

- **Self-assessment** of green start-ups with scientific support
- **Calculation of the future CO₂e reduction potential** through the start-up's products and services (no CO₂ footprinting)
- **Fair comparison** between start-up solution and reference product
- **Focus on significant differences in emissions**, no complete comparative life cycle assessment (LCA)
- **Forecast using sales projection** for the next five years
- **Result:** Planned climate mitigation potential of the start-up with successful market entry

[Detailed description of the methodology on page 37](#)

Transformation-oriented green start-ups have the potential to reduce **30,000 tonnes of CO₂e annually**.

This corresponds to the climate mitigation contribution of **seven modern wind turbines**, which supply 24,000 households with electricity, as well as an economic value of **€ 2.4 million per year for climate mitigation** per start-up.

Green start-ups have a **considerable climate mitigation potential**

For transformation-oriented green start-ups, an average climate mitigation potential of **30,000 tons of CO₂e** per year can be assumed.

The climate mitigation potential of individual green start-ups varies considerably: while some start-ups achieve annual climate mitigation potentials of just a few hundred tons of CO₂e, others achieve potentials of hundreds of thousands of tons per year.

Translating the climate mitigation potential into an economic value by multiplying it by a CO₂ price of € 80*, it corresponds to a monetary **value of € 2.4 million per year** per transformation-oriented green start-up. This shows for the first time the ecological side of the double dividend as an economic value.

* based on the average CO₂ price for 2022/23 in the European Emissions Trading System.

Practical examples of the climate mitigation potential

Better SOL GmbH (founded in 2022) inspects and sells used solar modules and thus avoids the energy- and resource-intensive production of new modules. For every 1 kWp of second-life solar module output, approx. 800 kg of CO₂e emissions are reduced, meaning that Better SOL achieves a climate mitigation potential of **9,600 tons of CO₂e/year** with the planned company growth.

Climate mitigation potential of **Better SOL**

” The advantage of having a concrete figure for our contribution to climate mitigation enables us to communicate this to our customers and potential donors, but also to constantly measure ourselves and make targeted improvements.

Luisa Schulze, founder

Trailer Dynamics GmbH (founded in 2018) develops battery-electric drives for semi-trailers, which can reduce diesel consumption by an average of 40% and increase the range of e-trucks. Emissions are reduced by around 2,900 kg CO₂e per vehicle, meaning that Trailer Dynamics will achieve a climate mitigation potential of **30,800 tons of CO₂e/year** with the planned expansion of production.

Climate mitigation potential of **Trailer Dynamics**

” We are shaping the future of sustainable logistics by creating the basis for emission-free freight transportation. Through innovation and environmentally friendly solutions, we are making an active contribution to climate mitigation and the green transformation of the transportation sector.

Abdullah Jaber, CEO

Practical examples of the climate mitigation potential

e|Hy elementarhy **elementarhy GmbH** (founded in 2024) develops resource- and cost-efficient membrane technology for green hydrogen production - with two strong climate mitigation effects: faster scaling of green hydrogen production, which emits approx. 75% less CO₂e compared to fossil hydrogen, and an approx. 95% reduction in critical raw material requirements, e.g. iridium, compared to comparable technologies. By scaling up its ongoing pilot production, elementarhy is projected to achieve a climate mitigation potential of **935,000 tons of CO₂e/year**.

➔ Climate mitigation potential of **elementarhy**

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The reduction of CO₂ emissions, critical raw materials and costs through elementarhy's technology enables the energy transition and strengthens the security of supply.

Arne Birth, CFO/CMO

Train4Impact* offers free webinars, workshops and individual coachings on the topic of sustainability and impact assessments for start-ups.

As a start-up, you can book 1:1 coaching to calculate your climate mitigation potential directly here or register for one of the many workshops:

[🔗 impactnexus.io/t4i](https://impactnexus.io/t4i)

Start-up supporters can adapt and integrate the Train4Impact offerings into their program free of charge. Register at:

[🔗 start-green.net/train4impact/](https://start-green.net/train4impact/)

*Funded by the European Union and the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy through the European Social Fund Plus (ESF Plus).

3

SPOTLIGHTS

Latest results from the **research community**

With the new “Spotlights“ format, we invite colleagues from the research community to present their latest results and findings on green start-ups and their specific challenges and potential in the Green Startup Report. To this end, we make the Green Startup

Report’s impact data pool available for additional evaluations and enable interested researchers to contribute their own data sources and current research findings. In this way, we are expanding the data and knowledge base on the conditions for the success of green start-ups, rel-

evant trends and the necessary design of start-up and innovation ecosystems. In this way, we are pooling the latest knowledge on the need for action for sustainable entrepreneurship and the success of the major transformation tasks ahead of us.

SPOTLIGHT AI

Generative AI in green start-ups

Junior Professor Dr. Jeanine Kirchner-Krath heads the “Digitalization and Sustainable Business” research group at the University of Koblenz.

In the Spotlight, she presents the results of an in-depth sample survey based on the GSR dataset. She explores the question of how green start-ups use generative AI and the challenges they face.

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For me personally, a new era has begun: use your creativity and ideas and create added value for society with the help of various AI tools.

Anonymous response from one of the green start-ups surveyed

→ Use of generative AI in various business model areas

in % of all green start-ups surveyed

Based on an anonymized survey of 128 green start-ups conducted in winter 2024/25.

SPOTLIGHT AI

Generative AI finds its way into business models of green start-ups

87.5% already use generative artificial intelligence (AI) in one or more areas of their company.

Generative AI is most frequently used in the areas of marketing and sales (66%), followed by support for operational activities (49%).

47% of green start-ups also use generative AI specifically for the (further) development of their value proposition. They consider AI as a creative sparring partner that helps them to optimize their impact in a targeted manner. Generative AI therefore has the potential to further strengthen the "double dividend" – economic success and sustainable impact – of green start-ups.

SPOTLIGHT AI

Generative AI poses challenges

Green start-ups currently still see major challenges that stand in the way of unlocking the potential of generative AI. In particular, **technological challenges** are listed, e.g. with regard to the quality and reliability of AI-generated content.

The start-ups see **economic challenges** in the security and utilization of their data and in complying with the legal framework, among other things.

It is worth noting that green start-ups also see **social and environmental challenges**. In particular, the high energy consumption of generative AI is seen as a risk to its sustainable mission and integrity.

➔ Challenges for the use of generative AI in green start-ups in % of all green start-ups surveyed

Based on an anonymized survey of 128 green start-ups conducted in winter 2024/25.

As a company that is committed to sustainability, we are critical of the high energy intensity of many AI systems.

Anonymous response from a green start-up

“

With customized support programs for green start-ups, we have pursued the right strategy and carried out valuable pioneering work.

”

Oliver Krischer,
Minister for the Environment, Nature
and Transport in NRW

SPOTLIGHT NORTH RHINE WESTPHALIA (NRW)

Green start-ups in NRW

As a senior researcher at the Borderstep Institute, **Dr. Thomas Neumann** is responsible for investigating national and international ecosystems for green start-ups.

In the Spotlight, he presents how the Green Start-up Monitor NRW* is the first detailed analysis of the green start-up scene in a single federal state.

[🔗 Link to the Green Start-up Monitor NRW](#)

*Neumann et al. (2024)

SPOTLIGHT NRW

Support system for green start-ups in NRW is characterized by diversity and quality

→ Share of green start-ups that give the location a good or very good rating

Own figure according to Neumann et al. (2024) based on responses from 410 green start-ups surveyed in NRW and 1,657 surveys in other federal states.

The results of the Green Start-up Monitor NRW* show that **86% of green start-ups in North Rhine-Westphalia in 2023 rate their regional start-up ecosystem as good or very good** - a figure that is significantly higher than the national average of 56%.

Further surveys among start-ups and experts indicate that NRW stands out positively in a national comparison, particularly due to the close links between green start-ups and universities, the quality of public support services and the high technology orientation of green start-ups.

An inventory also shows that with a total of 16 specialized financing and support offers for green start-ups, NRW plays a pioneering role nationwide in terms of both the diversity and quality of the support system.

*Neumann et al. (2024)

➔ Preferred and received financing for green start-ups

■ preferred (NRW)
 ■ received (NRW)
 ■ received (other federal states)

Own figure according to Neumann et al. (2024) based on a survey of 347 green start-ups in NRW and 1,472 green start-ups in other federal states on average in 2020 and 2023.

➔ Share of green start-ups that cooperate with established companies

Own illustration according to Neumann et al. (2024) based on a survey of 927 green start-ups in NRW and 3,897 green start-ups in other federal states on average from 2020 to 2023.

SPOTLIGHT NRW

Venture capital and networking in NRW challenging

While raising capital is a nationwide problem, the gap between the need for venture capital and its allocation is particularly large for green start-ups in NRW. Almost half of all green start-ups in NRW prefer financing from business angels, but only 21% were able to realize this.

At the same time, it is clear that green start-ups in NRW cooperate much less frequently with established companies.

These discrepancies indicate a clear undersupply of venture capital and networking, which hinders both economic growth and the scaling of the impact of green start-ups. Given the strength of NRW as a business location, considerable potential is seen here.

SPOTLIGHT FUNDS

Climate focus **in funds**

Prof. Dr. Jörn Block is Professor of Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Sustainability Management at the University of Trier and Head of the Steinbeis Transfer Center for Technology and IP Management.

In the Spotlight, he presents the results of a survey of 694 fund managers conducted by the University of Trier and the European Investment Fund (EIF)*. The survey examined the extent to which venture capitalists take climate aspects into account in their investment decisions and what motives play a role in this.

[Link to the study](#)

* Block et al. (2024)

➔ Motives for consideration of climate factors in investments

Own figure based on a survey of 468 fund managers conducted in 2021 and presented in Block et al. (2024).

SPOTLIGHT FUNDS

Why funds focus on climate mitigation – between responsibility and market opportunities

More than 73% of respondents take climate factors into account in their investment decisions. For 56%, ethical responsibility is a priority, particularly for funds with female partners. Larger funds and private equity funds, on the other hand, primarily cite pressure from external stakeholders as a driving factor.

It is worth noting that almost half of respondents expect better investment performance by taking climate factors into account, once again confirming the economic relevance of green corporate strategy [see p.14.](#)

SPOTLIGHT FUNDS

Different strategies for sustainable investing

Most funds integrate climate factors into their investment decisions either by specifically excluding companies that do not meet certain climate and ESG criteria (negative screening) or by specifically investing in companies that have particularly high sustainability standards (positive screening).

It is striking that the motivation of the funds has a strong influence on the choice of strategy. Funds that take climate factors into account due to regulatory requirements or external pressure are particularly likely to exclude certain companies (negative screening). Funds that want to differentiate themselves strategically in the market through sustainability, on the other hand, tend to focus on the targeted financing of sustainable companies (positive screening) and on impact investing.

➔ Investment strategies that take climate factors into account

Own figure based on a survey of 468 fund managers conducted in 2021 and presented in Block et al. (2024).

4 | CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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The Green Startup Report is an important, scientifically sound addition to the German landscape of start-up studies, which are often based on surveys. By analyzing a mixture of primary and secondary data, the growing importance of green innovations is clearly demonstrated. This is accompanied by the positive role of funding programs, investor participation and women in management as well as the critical examination of AI from a sustainability perspective.

Dr. Florian Täube
Head of Entrepreneurship Department at the RKW Competence Center

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→ Making green start-ups and their impact visible and measurable in funding programs

The GSR shows that the proportion of green start-ups in important funding and financing programs such as EXIST and the High-Tech Gründerfonds is above average and growing continuously. As the founding teams do not receive a bonus for the environmental performance of their products and services in these programs, this is evidence of the technological and economic attractiveness of green start-ups. In order to be able to evaluate their growing importance and the impact of federal and state programs in a more targeted manner, **green start-ups should be systematically recorded as a separate category in statistics and evaluations in the future** - based on EUROSTAT's EGSS classification for environmental products and services. In addition, the actual contribution of the funded start-ups to the ecological transformation should also be recorded. The GHG & Impact Estimator presented on [p.37](#) provides a sound methodology for evaluating the climate mitigation potential of individual start-ups or entire programs on the basis of data. This creates transparency and comparability and provides important insights into the contribution of these programs as well as a basis for their development.

→ “AI literacy”: targeted funding of the sustainable use of AI in start-ups

88% of the green start-ups surveyed already use generative AI, particularly for marketing and sales. At the same time, 34% see the use of generative AI as a significant risk to their sustainable mission and integrity, partly due to the high energy consumption. Training and advisory services on the use of AI to increase impact and the use of more resource-efficient AI models should therefore be included in start-up funding offers, e.g. with the help of „AI innovation vouchers“ and through integrative training and coaching offers, e.g. in accelerator programs.

→ Climate mitigation potential as a possible source of financing for green start-ups

With the GSR 2025, Borderstep provides the world's first figures on the climate mitigation potential of young innovative companies. On average, the potential of a single transformation-oriented green start-up is 30,000 tons of CO₂e per year. This corresponds to a value of around €2.4 million per company in the EU emissions trading system. Green start-ups thus generate positive external effects for which they have not yet been rewarded in the market context. In view of the financing challenges faced by green deep tech start-ups with long development and testing periods in particular, it should be examined whether climate mitigation services can be intelligently pre-financed. **Climate forward financing approaches promote or finance in advance** the emission reductions or carbon removals that can be achieved in the future through clearly defined climate mitigation measures. These approaches have not yet been developed for start-ups. Estimates by the Borderstep Institute assume an additional financing volume for green start-ups in Germany of over €6 billion per year.

→ Communicating the economic attractiveness of green start-ups for investments more effectively

This report shows that green business ideas are particularly well represented among growth-oriented start-ups with investment (29%). This high proportion underlines the scaling potential of green tech start-ups and their economic attractiveness. This makes them attractive both for investment funds that integrate climate and ESG criteria due to regulatory requirements, such as the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR), and in particular for funds that want to strategically differentiate themselves on the market through sustainability. For start-ups with green products and business models, it is therefore advisable **to analyze the specific characteristics of these funds and their investment strategies in advance and adapting the pitch deck accordingly**. As the study by Block et al. presented in the „Spotlights“ section shows, the probability of successful financing or at least an invitation to a personal pitch increases significantly.

“ This GSR contains a number of data and method-related improvements compared to previous publications. In particular, commercial register data (filtered in advance by startupdetector) is now available in non-anonymized form, which offers many more options for analysis and data supplementation than anonymized data. The differentiation of startups according to the criteria “innovative” and “growth-oriented” could be made even more precise by startupdetector. The distinction between green and non-green start-ups is appropriate and transparent. It would be beneficial if international comparisons were possible, such as in the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM). The need for an annual cross-sectional study, which could gradually take on a longitudinal character, exists in science as well as in start-up policy and is growing.

Prof. Dr. Rolf Sternberg

Head of the Germany country team of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM)

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5 | RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Data basis

A comprehensive analysis of commercial register data was carried out for the first time for the Green Startup Report 2025. It is based on a complete survey of all start-ups in Germany in the legal form of a corporation (UG, GmbH, AG, etc.). This enables an objective and methodologically sound view of the green start-up scene.

The start-ups were identified by startupdetector GmbH, which systematically analyzes commercial register entries. A multi-stage process was used that combines algorithmic filtering with manual checks. Only companies that are registered as a corporation and develop their own, usually innovative product and/or have the potential for strong growth

were classified as start-ups*.

As part of the Green Startup Report 2025, 17,954 commercial register entries of startups founded between January 2019 and December 2024 were examined on this basis.

In addition, 53,034 commercial register entries on investments made in start-ups were analyzed. This includes capital increases with external investors and the participation of various sources of financing such as venture capital and business angels. This means that, for the first time, reliable statements can be made about how green start-ups differ from other start-ups in terms of their financing structure.

1. Analysis of all start-ups recorded in the commercial register

100,000 newly founded companies per year

2. Automatic verification of whether the companies meet the criteria for a start-up

approx. 80 % not innovative or not growth-oriented

3. Renewed manual review of all potential start-ups

approx. 17 % not innovative or not growth-oriented

4. Final selection of innovative and growth-oriented start-ups

approx. 3 % of all newly founded companies are start-ups

* A detailed description of how startupdetector identifies startups can be found here: <https://www.startupdetector.de/datenbank/>

Differentiation between green and non-green start-ups

Green start-ups are innovative and growth-oriented young companies that contribute to the ecological goals of a green economy with their products or services.

The distinction between green and non-green start-ups is based **on the European Commission's Environmental Goods and Services Sector (EGSS) classification system***, whose keyword list was expanded to over 400 specific terms for the study. This contains keywords that describe products and services of the green economy and serve as a central reference for the classification.

A **three-stage semi-automated process** was developed to ensure a valid classification.

1 Comparison of company data with the EGSS keyword list to identify potential green start-ups.

2 Analysis of company websites using Large Language Models (LLMs) to identify evidence of primary activity in the Green Economy. Companies without sufficient online information are excluded.

3 Manual review of the potential green start-ups identified in step 1 or 2 by experienced reviewers.

The result is a clear distinction between **2,113 green and 10,148 non-green start-ups** that were founded between 2019 and 2024.

The methodology was **validated through sample checks and comparisons with external data sources**, including a complete manual review of 571 EXIST-funded start-ups. The results show a high degree of **accuracy and reliability: less than 1%** of EXIST start-ups were incorrectly not recognized as green (false negatives) and **also less than 1% were incorrectly classified as green** (false positives).

17,954 start-ups founded between 2019 and 2024

12,261 start-ups for which sufficient data is available

2,113 green start-ups that can be clearly assigned to the green economy

Sound estimation of climate mitigation potential with the GHG & Impact Estimator

The data presented in this GSR 2025 on the climate protection potential of start-ups was collected using the “**GHG & Impact Estimator**“ **online tool** developed by Borderstep and ImpactNexus and is based on the Borderstep Institute’s impact database.

Start-ups use the “GHG & Impact Estimator“ to carry out a **scientifically supported self-assessment** and estimate the planned climate mitigation contribution of their products and services for the next 5 years. A **fair and transparent comparison** is made between the start-up solution and a conventional reference product.

The GHG & Impact Estimator provides a standardized calculation method with extensive support. **The focus is exclusively on the material emission-related differences.** No full comparative life cycle analysis (LCA) is carried out, but fundamental LCA approaches and rules are followed. The quantified difference in emissions is then extrapolated with a realistic sales forecast for the start-up to determine **an average annual climate mitigation potential** over the next five years.

This climate mitigation potential reflects the future achievable impact of the start-up if it successfully enters the market. The methodology of the GHG & Impact Estimator is **based on international best practices** of forward-looking impact assessment, including the Impact Management Project and Project Frame.

The **expert-based calculation** of an average annual climate mitigation potential of 30,000 tons of CO₂e for particularly growth- and impact-oriented start-ups published here is based on over 15 peer-reviewed assessments.

specific CO₂e reduction per product/service unit compared to the reference product **×** **planned sales development** over the next 5 years **=** **climate mitigation potential**

More information on the methodology of the GHG & Impact Estimator can be found in the background paper: [Sustainability assessment of start-ups with the ESG Starter and the GHG & Impact Estimator](#)

Authorship

Prof. Dr. Klaus Fichter is Director of the Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability. He teaches at the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, where he holds the professorship for Innovation Management and Sustainability (PIN). He is a member of the executive committee of the FGF Research Network Entrepreneurship, Innovation and SMEs and initiated the „Sustainable Entrepreneurship“ working group.

Dr. Thomas Neumann supports the Sustainable Entrepreneurship research area of the Borderstep Institute as a senior researcher. The start-up coach, scientist and lecturer works at the interface of entrepreneurship theory and business practice and has already supervised over 300 start-up projects. His research focuses on the micro- and macroeconomic impact measurement of start-ups.

Prof. Dr. Yasmin Olteanu is Professor of Business Administration / Entrepreneurship at the Berliner Hochschule für Technik (BHT) and Borderstep Research Fellow. From September 2018 to February 2021, she worked as a research associate in the field of Sustainable Entrepreneurship at the Borderstep Institute. Among other things, she was responsible for the development of the Green Startup Report.

Tim Grothey is a research associate at the Borderstep Institute. As an industrial engineer, he manages and supports projects in the research field of sustainable entrepreneurship and develops methods for future-oriented impact assessment. In his research work, he is particularly interested in impact-oriented approaches that tackle the challenges of climate change with sustainable innovations.

Publisher

The Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability gGmbH

researches the future and examines what is to come (innovation) and what will remain (sustainability). With our scientific work, we analyze problem solutions for a sustainable economy and develop future-oriented action strategies for companies, start-ups, associations, funding institutions and politics.

As an independent and non-profit research institution, Borderstep is active in the field of application-oriented innovation and entrepreneurship research and is committed to the guiding principle of sustainable development.

Our aim is to generate new problem-oriented knowledge that moves the world! We see ourselves as scientific pioneers of change and want to contribute to a green transformation of economic processes and lifestyles on the basis of excellent research. In doing so, we strengthen and support those pioneers and innovators in society who make sustainability a practical reality.

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